

GEOLOGICAL FACTORS FOR THE FORMATION OF THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF GROUNDWATER IN THE CATCHMENT AREA OF THE PCHELINA RESERVOIR, BULGARIA

Mila Trayanova-Koleva¹, Sava Kolev¹, Aleksey Benderev¹ and Stefan Tsakovski²

¹Geological Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev 24, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria. E-mail: milatr@abv.bg, sava.koleff@abv.bg, alekseybenderev@yahoo.com

²Chair of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Sofia, J Bourchier Blvd. 1, 1164 Sofia, Bulgaria. E-mail: stsakovski@chem.uni-sofia.bg

ABSTRACT: *The main objective of the present study is to clarify the geological conditions which affect the chemical composition of groundwater in the catchment area of Pchelina Reservoir. In order to determine the distribution of rocks types predetermining the regional regularities for the formation of different chemical composition of groundwater, the proposed by Kehaiov approach is applied. The obtained results show that, as a result of the geological structure, low mineralized groundwater with good quality characteristics predominates in the area. The localization of areas with an increased content of given hydrochemical indicators in the subsequent analysis within the implementation of the project "Development of integrated methodology for dams' chemical impact assessment on adjacent surface water bodies (DIMDAMS)" will allow the easier distinguishment of the possible polluted areas of anthropogenic genesis.*

Key words: *groundwater, chemical composition, geological factors, Pchelina Reservoir*

INTRODUCTION

Groundwater is one of the most important natural resources. Underground aquifers supply drinking water and much of the water used for irrigation. Thus the quality of groundwater is as important as its quantity, owing to the suitability of water for these various purposes. At the same time variation in groundwater quality in an area is a function of physical and chemical parameters that are greatly influenced by natural and anthropogenic factors. For this reason, in order to be able to assess the degree of anthropogenic influence, it is first important to clarify the geological conditions, as the chemical composition of groundwater is largely determined by the regional geology and aquifer characteristics (Güler & Thyne 2004; Gerginov *et al.* 2019; Gong *et al.* 2023, Mihailova *et al.* 2023). Groundwater chemistry depends on a factors such as general geology, degree of chemical weathering of the various rock types, the longer residence time of water, etc. The physicochemical characteristics of groundwater is influenced also by different chemical processes occurring during rock-water interaction, including dissolution/precipitation, ion exchange reaction, oxidation and reduction (Frape & Fritz 1984; Velikov 1986; Penchev *et al.* 1990; Edmund *et al.* 2002; Appelo & Postma 2005; Elango & Kannan 2007).

The object of the present study is the catchment area of the Pchelina Reservoir, located in Southwestern Bulgaria, Pernik Province. This area was selected as a pilot in the frames of the Project "Development of integrated methodology for dams' chemical impact assessment on adjacent surface water bodies (DIMDAMS)", funded by the Ministry of Education and Science, Bulgarian National Science Fund. The main objective of the study is to clarify the geological conditions which affect the chemical composition of groundwater in the considered area, in order to assess the anthropogenic influence during the subsequent analysis within the project.

STUDY AREA

Pchelina Reservoir has been in operation since 1975. Its construction took place by blocking Struma River near the village of Lobosh by an earth-fill dam with a length of over 600 m. The reservoir waters flooded also the mouth of Svetlya River – a right tributary of the Struma River. The name of the reservoir is related to the displaced and obliterated village of Pchelintsi, located in this place. The total volume of the Pchelina Reservoir is 54.8 million m³ (of which the useful volume is 19.3 million m³), its area is 5.38 km² and its depth reaches 19 m (Gartsyanova 2017). The waters of the reservoir are used as a source for industrial water supply, irrigation and as recreation area.

The catchment area of the reservoir amounts to 1287.6 km² and covers the hollows of Radomir, Pernik and Breznik and the adjacent slopes of the mountains Zavalska, Viskyar, Lyulin, Vitoshka, Verila,

Konyavska, Golo bardo, Cherna gora, Rudini, Erulska, Lyubash. Its altitude changes from about 600 m near the Pchelina Reservoir dam to 2290 m at the summit of Vitosha Mountain (Cherni vrah peak).

The terrain is well-drained by an intensively developed river network. Its main drainage artery is the Struma River with its tributaries Svetlya, Konska, etc. In terms of climate, the area belongs to the transitional continental climate and the average annual precipitation is in the range of 550-700 mm/m². The hydrogeological conditions in the basin are controlled less by the major tectonic structures than by minor internal grabens and horsts.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

To determine the influence of geological factors on hydrogeological conditions and formation of the initial chemical composition of groundwater, clarifying the spatial distribution of the different rock types is needed. This determines the conditions for formation and movement of groundwater relevant to the character and the contact time between them and the water-bearing medium. The main output information for the purpose are GIS layers of the Geological Maps of Bulgaria at a scale of 1:100 000.

When analyzing the available information, it is established that in the considered region prevails diverse in genesis, mineralogical and petrographic composition rocks that are characterized by different collector and conductive properties in relation to groundwater.

To determine the distribution of rocks predetermining the regional regularities for the formation of different chemical composition of groundwater the proposed by Kehaiov approach is applied. Its used at the compilation of a Hydrogeochemical map of Bulgaria in M 1:200 000 (Kehaiov et al. 1993) and divides the common rocks in Bulgaria according to their chemical, mineralogical and petrographic composition in 11 main groups:

- I. Deluvial deposits, clayey sands and clays of different ages;
- II. Marls, argillites, siltstones, etc.;
- III. Quartzites, arkosic sandstones, sandstones, conglomerates, etc.;
- IV. Flysch formations, as well as formations in which it is difficult to distinguish the rock type due to frequent changes in the profile of the filtration medium;
- V. Carbonate rocks – limestones, dolomites, marbles;
- VI. Alluvial, alluvial-proluvial deposits;
- VII. Loess, loess-like deposits and sub-loess gravels;
- VIII. Volcanogenic-sedimentary formations of the Upper Cretaceous and Paleogene;
- IX. Acid igneous and metamorphic rocks;
- X. Medium acid igneous and metamorphic rocks;
- XI. Basic and ultrabasic igneous and metamorphic rocks.

After analyzing the geological structure of the catchment area of the Pchelina Reservoir using this approach, and the hydrogeological information presented in the Explanatory note to the hydrogeological map of the Republic of Bulgaria in M 1:200 000 (Yovchev & Altovski 1975), it was established which of the 11 separate groups are distributed in the area under consideration and what characteristics are expected for the groundwater in them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the regional assessment of the influence of the chemical, mineralogical and petrographic composition of the rocks according to Kehaiov's classification, in the catchment area of the Pchelina Reservoir 9 groups of rocks were established (figure 1).

- Marls, argillites, siltstones, etc.:

Two types of groundwater are formed in them: fissure-porous, related to the weathering zone, and fissure-vein – at the tectonically disturbed zones. Below the weathering zone, the rocks are not water-bearing and are perceived as a regional aquitard. Fissure-porous groundwater has the widest distribution. It is fresh and ultra-fresh of the hydrocarbonate-calcium-magnesium type, with a mineralization of 0.090 to 0.527 g/l. The springs have small flow rates, from 0.010 to 0.500 l/s.

- Quartzites, arkosic sandstones, sandstones, conglomerates, etc.:

Groundwater in the complex is related to the sandstones. In the zone of free circulation small porous streams are formed, discharged by a small number of springs with a flow rate of 0.010-0.020 l/s. At depth, the water in the sandstones is fissure-stratified. The hydraulic conductivity (k) is very low, varying from 0.1 to 0.27 m/d. Groundwater is fresh, hydrocarbonate-calcium-magnesium-sodium type.

Figure 1. Location of the catchment area of the Pchelina Reservoir and types of water-bearing medium according to the classification of Kehaiov et al. Legend: 1. Reservoir, 2. Marls, argillites, siltstones, etc., 3. Quartzites, arkosic sandstones, sandstones, conglomerates, etc., 4. Flysch formations, as well as formations in which it is difficult to distinguish the rock type due to frequent changes in the profile of the filtration medium, 5. Carbonate rocks – limestones, dolomites, marbles, 6. Alluvial, alluvial-proluvial deposits, 7. Volcanogenic-sedimentary formations of the Upper Cretaceous and Paleogene, 8. Acid igneous and metamorphic rocks, 9. Medium acid igneous and metamorphic rocks, 10. Basic and ultrabasic igneous and metamorphic rocks

- Flysch formations, as well as formations in which it is difficult to distinguish the rock type due to frequent changes in the profile of the filtration medium:

The lithological composition does not allow the formation and accumulation of streams with large flow rates. This is confirmed by the springs attached, the flow rate of which does not exceed 0.150 l/s. Although small, the flow rates are quite stable. The water of the springs is fresh, hydrocarbonate-calcium-magnesium type.

- Carbonate rocks – limestones, dolomites, marbles:

The aquifer profile is represented by limestones, dolomitic limestones, dolomites, oolitic sandstones and sandy marls. The total thickness of the aquifer varies from 200 to 600 m. The intense tectonic movements have detached the horizon and broken its hydraulic unity. Individual blocks in most cases have their own hydraulic regime. The limestones and dolomites are highly fractured and karstified. The nature of the karstification in individual parts of the region is different. With relatively larger flow rates are the springs connected to the materials of the Middle and Upper Triassic in its outcrops along Golo Bardo and south of it. Here, several springs have a flow rate of over 40 l/s. The regime of the springs is unstable. In terms of chemical composition, the water of the springs is fresh, hydrocarbonate-calcium-magnesium type.

- Alluvial, alluvial-proluvial deposits:

Quaternary sediments fill most of the hollows in the area. There groundwater is formed in the sandy layers and lenses of the Struma River and its tributaries. In terms of chemical composition, the groundwater formed in the Quaternary sediments is fresh, hydrocarbonate-calcium-magnesium-sodium type.

- Volcanogenic-sedimentary formations:

Groundwater is accumulated and circulates in the cracks of the tuffs and tuffites. The rest of the rock types that make up the complex are almost waterless. The groundwater connected to the exposed parts of the complex is hydrocarbonate-calcium-magnesium-sodium type, discharged by springs with a flow rate of 0.010 to 6,000 l/s, with the predominance of springs with a flow rate of up to 0.100 l/s.

- Acid and medium acid igneous and metamorphic rocks:

They are mainly represented by gabbrodiorites, diorites, granodiorites, granites, etc. Two types of water are discharged from them: fissure-porous and fissure-vein. According to its chemical composition, it is fresh and ultra-fresh, mainly hydrocarbonate-calcium-magnesium type. Below the weathering zone, the intrusive rocks are practically non-aqueous (except for sporadic water circulating along faults).

- Basic and ultrabasic igneous and metamorphic rocks:

They are mainly represented by phyllitoid schists, diabases, diabase tuffs, diabase breccias and diabase porphyrites. Three types of groundwater are distributed in them: fissure-porous with shallow circulation, linked to the weathering zone, stratified-karst with local distribution and fissure-vein, attached to tectonically disturbed zones, faults, etc. Below the weathering zone, the diabase-phyllitoid aquifers are practically non-water-bearing. Fissure-porous groundwater has the greatest distribution. It is fresh and ultra-fresh, hydrocarbonate-calcium-magnesium type.

Figure 2. Piper diagram of groundwater in the catchment area of the Pchelina Reservoir compared with the type of water-bearing medium

In many of the chemical analyzes of the samples, data on sodium and bicarbonate concentrations are missing, which does not allow them to be plotted on a Piper diagram. This applies especially to water sources with a small flow, which are not of practical interest and are not used by the population. From the available information summarized above, it can be concluded that the rock types distributed in the studied area are a prerequisite for the presence mostly of fresh and ultra-fresh groundwater of hydrocarbonate-calcium-magnesium type (figure 2). However, it should be mentioned that along with the regional hydrogeological and hydrochemical features, the geological conditions could be reason for probable presence of local anomalies associated with faults and pegmatite veins in which they are established ore occurrences, as well as springs with thermal waters. Each of them is a local source that can cause local anomalies regarding some components of the chemical composition of fresh groundwater.

CONCLUSION

The geological structure of the catchment area of the Pchelina Reservoir has a leading importance for the chemical composition of the groundwater. It is a regional prerequisite for the formation of fresh groundwater, mostly of hydrocarbonate-calcium-magnesium type. Against the background of relatively low

mineralized water with a similar composition, the presence of natural anomalies due to established accumulations of ore mineralization and the places of outflow of thermal water on the surface is possible. The obtained results show that, as a result of the geological structure, low mineralized groundwater with good quality characteristics predominates in the area. The localization of areas with an increased content of given hydrochemical indicators in the subsequent analysis within the implementation of the project "Development of integrated methodology for dams' chemical impact assessment on adjacent surface water bodies (DIMDAMS)" will allow the easier distinguishment of the possible polluted areas of anthropogenic genesis.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Ministry of Education and Science, Bulgarian National Science Fund, Grant КП-06-ПН79/19 "Development of integrated methodology for dams' chemical impact assessment on adjacent surface water bodies (DIMDAMS)".

REFERENCES

- Appelo C., Postma D. 2005: *Geochemistry, Groundwater and Pollution*, Balkema Publishers, 672 pp.
- Edmunds W., Carrillo-Rivera J., Cardona A. 2002: *Geochemical evolution of groundwater beneath Mexico City*, *Journal of Hydrology*, 254, pp. 1-24
- Elango L., Kannan R. 2007: *Rock-Water Interaction and Its Control on Chemical Composition of Groundwater*, In: Sarkar D., Datta R., Hannigan R. (Eds.), *Developments in Environmental Science*, Vol. 5, pp. 229-243, Amsterdam, Elsevier
- Frape S., Fritz P., McNutt R. 1984: *Water-rock interaction and chemistry of groundwaters from the Canadian Shield*, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta*, 48, pp. 1617-1627
- Gartsyanova K. 2017: *Assessment of the water quality of the "Pchelina" Reservoir*, *Probl. Geogr*, 1, pp. 62-71
- Gerginov P., Kerestedzhian T., Toteva A., Mihaylova B., Benderev A. 2019: *Geological environment, groundwater quality and regulatory*, *Water Affairs*, 5/6, pp. 19-29 (in Bulgarian with English abstract)
- Gong Z., Tian X., Fu L., Niu H., Xia Z., Ma Z., Chen J., Zhou Y. 2023: *Chemical Characteristics and Controlling Factors of Groundwater in Chahannur Basin.*, *Water*, 15, 1524, 16 pp.
- Güler C., Thyne G. 2004: *Hydrologic and geologic factors controlling surface and groundwater chemistry in Indian Wells-Owens Valley area, southeastern California, USA*, *Journal of Hydrology*, 285 (1-4), pp. 177-198
- Kehaiov T., Stoyanov I., Shopova Y., Naydenova S., Teneva S., Segmenski L. 1993: *Hydrogeochemical map of Bulgaria in M 1: 200 000*, National Geofund
- Mihailova B., Kerestedjian T., Peneva A., Benderev A. 2023: *Geological factors for the formation of the chemical composition of groundwater in the catchment area of the Mesta river*, *Engineering Geology and Hydrogeology*, 37, pp. 61-88
- Penchev P., Borosov S., Velikov B., Lakov A., Spasov K. 1990: *Hydrogeology and Engineering geology*, Sofia, Technica, 342 pp. (in Bulgarian)
- Velikov B. 1986: *Hydrochemistry of groundwater*, Higher Institute of Mining and Geology, Sofia, 280 pp. (in Bulgarian)
- Yovchev J., Altovski M. (eds.). 1975: *Explanatory note to the hydrogeological map of the Republic of Bulgaria in M 1:200 000*, National Geofund

